

The anatomy response of several rice varieties (*Oryza sativa* L.) in Gunungkidul rainfed land, Yogyakarta, Indonesia

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ABSTRACT

Rice is consumed as the main source of carbohydrates, with various types. Rice varieties (*Oryza sativa* L.) vary in inbred, hybrid and local rice. The difference was caused by the process and local genetic resources not the result of inbred or hybrid crosses. This study aims to determine the anatomical response of several rice varieties grown in rainfed land. This study used a complete randomized block design with 6 rice varieties as treatment, namely Hipa 9, Inpari blast, Inpari 33, Inpari 43, Ciherang and local rice Sembada Merah. The study was conducted from October 2017 to January 2018 in Semanu, Gunungkidul, Indonesia. The anatomical parameters of the leaves measured included upper and lower epidermal cell thickness, cuticle in the upper and lower epidermis, mesophyll thickness in the major and minor interveina regions. Observations were carried out 5 times (major and minor interveina areas). The data obtained were analyzed by Analysis of variance and DMRT advanced test using SAS version 9.2. Besides that, cluster analysis was based on leaf anatomy to obtain dendrogram. The results showed significant anatomical differences (thickness of cuticles and epidermal thickness) among varieties planted. Each variety shows its genetic response to the environment because it is planted in rainfed land with limited water conditions. Clustering of anatomically based leaf varieties (thickness of cuticles and epidermal thickness both above and below in the major and minor interveina regions) there were 3 groups. Cluster I: Inpari 42 and Inpari 33; cluster II: Inpari blast, Ciherang and Sembada merah; and hybrid rice groups: Hipa 9 as cluster III.

Keywords : respons, anatomy, rice, Gunungkidul, Indonesia

INTRODUCTION

The productivity of upland rice /fields in Indonesia is still very diverse, ranging from 1.9 t/ha - 4 t/ha with an average of 3.12 tons/ha (Central Bureau of Statistics 2011). Improved production techniques such as the use of improved varieties, improved cultivation techniques and control of pests and plant diseases, upland rice productivity can be reach around 4.4 - 5.4ton/ha (Guswara et al. 1998; Wahyuni 2008). Rainfed rice fields are one of the resources that are

still potential to be used as a source of food production growth. Rainfed paddy fields in the Gunungkidul area of Yogyakarta cover an area of 44,000 ha from a total of 117,704 ha of dry land (BPS DIY 2015). The productivity of rice in Gunungkidul rainfed lowland is 4,476 kg/ha on average (BPS DIY 2015) with a contribution to grain production in DIY at 21.79%. The productivity yield gap between rainfed lowland rice and irrigated lowland rice is very striking, which is 1,824 kg/ha, productivity of 4,476 kg/ha rainfed lowland rice and 6,300 kg / ha irrigated lowland rice (BPS DIY 2015).

One of the obstacles in increasing rice production is the limited genetic potential of cultivated rice varieties. Therefore, new high yielding varieties that are high yielding, early maturity and adequacy of the main elements for plant life are needed. The instability of rice productivity can be caused both internally and externally. External factors that influence agricultural productivity are climate change. As explained by Supriyanto (2013) is a large and varied abiotic stress affects the productivity of a plant. Dryness is one of the abiotic stresses that often occurs mainly on dry land. Drought stress affects changes in anatomy, morphology, physiology and biochemistry and disruption of plant growth and development such as stomatal closure, gas exchange restriction, leaf abortion (Heidary et al., 2007).

According to Purwanto (2012), drought stress can be overcome in two ways, namely minimizing stress factors by changing the environment or improving plant genotypes to reduce stress. The first way is difficult because it requires expensive and large costs so that the thing that is possible to do is the second method, improve plant genotypes to resist drought stress.

Drought-resistant rice genotype is a type of upland rice. In addition to upland rice, the Indonesian Agency for Agricultural Research and Development through the Center for Rice Research has released many site-specific rice superior varieties (VUBs) that have resistance to biotic stresses and tolerance to abiotic stress.

Based on these matters, this study aims to determine the anatomical response of several rice varieties grown in rainfed land.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was conducted from October 2017 to January 2018 in Semanu, Gunungkidul, Indonesia. This study used a complete randomized block design with 6 rice varieties as treatment, namely Hipa 9, Inpari blast, Inpari 33, Inpari 43, Ciherang and local rice Sembada merah. Leaf samples are taken before harvest time. The method of slicing rice leaves using a free hand section, then made semi-permanent preparations that have been penetrated with safranin.

The microscope used is BOECO BM-180, using the Optilab Advance Plus version made by miconos.

The anatomical parameters of the leaves measured included upper and lower epidermal cell thickness, cuticle in the upper and lower epidermis, mesophyll thickness in the major and minor intervena regions. Observations were carried out 5 times (both for major and minor intervena areas).

The data obtained were analyzed by variant (ANOVA = Analysis of variance) and Duncan's advanced test using SAS version 9.2. Besides that, clustering / cluster analysis is based on leaf anatomy to obtain dendogram.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Anatomic parameters measured were upper epidermis, upper cuticle in the upper epidermis, mesophyll, lower epidermis, and cuticle in the lower epidermis. The anatomical appearance of the leaves (upper epidermis, cuticle in the upper epidermis, mesophyll, lower epidermis, and cuticle in the lower epidermis is presented in Figure 1 (major intervena and minor intervena). From the anatomical appearance, the upper epidermis thickness, cuticle thickness in the upper epidermis mesophyll / width of the minor and major intervena leaves, lower epidermis, and cuticle in the lower epidermis can be seen. The results of analysis of variance of epidermal thickness, cuticle and major intervena width and minor intervena parameters are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Results of analysis of variance in thickness of cuticles, epidermis and width of major and minor intervena leaves in several varieties

Variety	Interverna major (micro meter)					Interverna minor (micro meter)				
	tka	TEa	Idy	teB	tKB	tka	TEa	Idy	teB	tKB
Hipa 9	2.53c	4.06ab	155.65a	3.68b	2.97d	5.21a	4.17b	106.53a	5.63ab	3.65a
Inpari Blas	4.05ab	5.76a	145.78b	6.43a	5.61a	4.04ac	4.56ab	89.57bc	4.81bc	3.63a
Inpari 42	4.73ab	4.60ab	176.62a	5.39a	4.04bc	4.67ab	4.38ab	95.52ab	4.41bc	4.11a
Ciherang	5.19a	4.89ab	153.071	6.49a	4.77b	4.44ab	4.44ab	81.59c	4.52bc	4.10a
Inpari 33	3.99ab	5.15ab	174.32b	5.96a	4.16bc	5.83ab	5.83a	84.90bc	6.63ba	3.46a
Sembada Merah	3.51bc	5.36a	125.25c	6.37a	3.79cd	4.56ab	4.56ab	76.24c	3.80a	3.14a
CV	24.5	16.51	8.57	15.70	15.07	24.03	24.03	10.49	17.32	27.5

Numbers followed by the same letter in the same row and column are not significantly different according to Duncan's Multiple Distance Test at the 5% level

Note: tka = thick upper cuticle; tEa = thick epidermis above; Idy = the width of the major intervena leaf; Idn = the width of the minor intervena leaf; teB = thickness of the lower epidermis; tKB = thick lower cuticle

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No	Varietas	Intervena major	Intervena minor
1	Hipa 9		
	Inpari blas		
	Inpari 42		
	ciherang		
	Inpari 33		
	Sembada merah		

Figure 1. The Anatomy of leaves of some rice varieties in Gunungkidul rainfed land, Indonesia

In Table 1, all observation parameters (thickness of cuticles, epidermal thickness) both in the major intervena and minor intervena were significantly different between the tested varieties except the thick cuticle lower intervena minor parameters. Anatomical differences in leaves quantified by the thickness of cuticles, epidermal thickness and leaf width according to the genetic potential of each variety and its response to environmental influences (because it was planted in Gunungkidul rainfed). These environmental conditions affect leaf anatomy, physiological parameters (plant height, leaf length, leaf width) and crop production. The response of each variety varies genetically that is affected by the environment. Table 2 showed that Inpari Blast varieties in physiologically, in terms of plant height, leaf length, and leaf width are the lowest among other varieties including productivity. Ciherang, Inpari 33 and Sembada Merah varieties have an average yield equal to or higher than the average yield on the plant description. Based on these factors, Ciherang, Inpari 33 and Sembada Merah local varieties are more adaptive to the conditions of rainfed land in Gunungkidul.

Table 2. Plant height, leaf length, leaf width and productivity of several rice varieties in rainfed land

Variety	Plant height (cm)	Leaf length (cm)	Leaf width (cm)	Productivity (ton/ha) DMG
Hipa 9	90.56	17.60	0.88	4.47
Inpari Blas	79.33	14.75	0.67	2.81
Inpari 42	87.11	29.84	1.04	6.73
Ciherang	102.33	20.24	0.95	7.57*
Inpari 33	96.67	21.75	0.95	6.60*
Sembada Merah	104.22	19.05	0.94	5.66*

Description: * equal or higher with average results on plant descriptions

In addition to the analysis of variance, cluster analysis was carried out in order to find out the differences between varieties based on leaf anatomy. Considering the variety tested is different from the origin of the plants, inbreds, hybrids and local varieties. Dendogram obtained from cluster analysis is presented in Figure 2.

Grouping of anatomically based leaf varieties (thickness of cuticles and epidermal thickness both above and below in the major and minor intervena regions) there were 3 groups. Group I: Inpari 42 and Inpari 33; group II: Inpari blast, Ciherang and Sembada merah; and hybrid rice groups: Hipa 9 as group III.

Hipa 9 variety is a distinct group different from other varieties because Hipa 9 is a hybrid variety, while other varieties are inbred varieties and local varieties. Genetically the origin of the variety is different and shows the differences in the anatomy of the leaves.

Figure 2. Dendrogram of 6 varieties based on leaf anatomy planted in Gunungkidul rainfed land

Description: **Hipa** = Hipa; **Blast** = Inpari Blas; **Ciherang** = Ciherang; **S.merah** = Sembada Merah; **Empat2** = Inpari 42; **Tiga3** = Inpari 33

CONCLUSIONS

In leaves anatomy (thickness of cuticles, major intervena epidermis and minor intervena), plant physiological parameters (plant height, leaf length, leaf width) and productivity of each variety showed a genetically influenced environment (rainfed land). Ciherang, Inpari 33 and Sembada Merah varieties were identified as the more adaptive to the conditions of rainfed land in Gunungkidul. Based on leaf anatomy, Hipa 9 variety is a hybrid variety as a separate group different from inbred varieties (Inpari blas, Inpari 42, Inpari 33, Ciherang) and local superior varieties Sembada Merah.

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